

**“UMUMIY O’RTA TA’LIM MAKTABLARINING 7-SINF
O’QUVCHILARIGA ZAMONAVIY ISSIQXONA MODELINI YASASH
TEXNOLOGIYASINI O’RGATISH METODIKASI”**

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3- kurs TT-301 guruh talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18154725>

Annotatsiya: Tuproq namligi va havo haroratini blyutuz yordamida boshqarib zamonaviy issiqxonani boshqarish masalasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Namlik suv oqimining tuproqdan o‘tishiga imkon beruvchi ikkita o‘yoqcha yordamida aniqlanadi. Havo harorati ham aniqlanib boshqariladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Tuproq, namlik, havo, harorat, Bluetooth to control soil, oynavand romlar, shaffof plyonkalar, yorug‘lik, avtomatik, suv, energiya, tejamkor, sensor, IT texnologiya.

Аннотация: Рассматривается вопрос управления современной теплицей с помощью Bluetooth для регулирования влажности почвы и температуры воздуха. Влажность определяется с помощью двух отверстий, обеспечивающих циркуляцию воды в почве. Температура воздуха также определяется и контролируется.

Ключевые слова: Почва, влажность, воздух, температура, Bluetooth для управления почвой, стеклянные рамы, прозрачные пленки, свет, автоматический режим, вода, энергия, энергосбережение, датчик, IT-технологии.

Annotation: The issue of controlling a modern greenhouse using Bluetooth to control soil moisture and air temperature is considered. Humidity is determined using two holes that allow water flow through the soil. Air temperature is also determined and controlled.

Key words: Soil, humidity, air, temperature, Bluetooth to control soil, glass frames, transparent films, light, automatic, water, energy, energy-saving, sensor, IT technology.

Natijalar:

Umumta’lim maktablarida texnologiya fanini o‘qitish jarayonida o‘quvchilarda 7-sinfda zamonaviy issiqxona modelini yasash texnologiyasini o‘qitishda kreativ yondashuvga oid ma’lumotlarni tadqiq qilish. Fan bo‘yicha mashg‘ulotlarni tashkil qilishda kasbiy shakllanish texnologiyasiga oid metodik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish.

Zamonaviy issiqxona — ustki oynavand romlar yoki shaffof plyonkalar yopilib, dehqonchilik qilinadigan mahsus joy bo'lib, ularda asosan ko'chat, ertagi savzavotlar, sitrus mevalar va pakana bo'yli mevali daraxt va butalarni, hamda, rezavorlar yetishtirishga ixtisoslashgan bo'ladi. Harorat, namlik va yorug'lik avtomatik boshqariladigan, suv va energiya tejamkor, sensorlar va IT texnologiyalar asosida ishlovchi yopiq inshoot.

Texnologik xarita

T/r	Ish ketma-ketligi	Ish eskizi yoki texnik rasmi	jihoz va moslamalar
1	<p>qurilish materiallaridan foneks,yog'och, bolt,gayka,mix,shrup va elektr istemolchilari,plastik shlang,plyonka olinadi</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">foneks</p>	<p>qurilish materiallaridan foneks,yog'och, bolt,gayka,mix,shrup , konselyar pichog'i,o'lchov metri,sirkul elektr istemolchilari, plastik shlang, plyonka</p>
2	<p>foneks kerakli o'lchamlarda kesib olinadi issiqxona asosi va karkaslari tayyorlanib kleylanadi.So'ngra plyonka karkasga tortib mahkamlanadi.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">foneksdan karkas tayyorlab olinadi</p>	<p>foneks, o'lchash asboblari, pichoq, kley</p>

<p>3</p>	<p>torfli shlanglar qotiriladi tuproqqa tortib</p>		<p>tofli tuproq, shlanglar</p>
	<p>karkasga tayyorlangan shurup qotiriladi va plata yelimlab yopishtiriladi eshik bilan tayyor yelimlab</p>		<p>eshik,shurup, bolt, gayka, plata, Arduino uno</p>
	<p>FC-28 tuproq namlik datchigi tuproqqa qotiriladi</p>		<p>FC-28 tuproq namlik datchigi, Arduino uno</p>

	<p>Suv nasosi va batareya ulanadi.</p>		<p>Arduino uno, motor shield drayveri, suv nasosi, batareya,sim</p>
	<p>Tuzilgan blyutuz sxemaga qurilmasi ulanadi</p>		<p>Arduino uno, maket platasi, blyutuz,sim</p>
	<p>Tayyor qurilmani masofadan boshqarish uchun smatfonga Bluetooth electronics ilovasi yuklab olinadi</p>		<p>Arduino uno, suv nasosi,batareya, sim,harorat datchigi, blyutuz,sim, smatfon</p>

Muhokama:

Fizik yetilgan tuproqning namligi plastiklik (nam holatda o'z shaklini saqlash) holatining eng quyi darajasiga yaqin turadi. Bu paytda haydalgan tuproq

yaxshi uvoqlanadi, yerni ishlash uchun ketadigan mehnat sarfi kamayadi va eng chidamli agregatlar hosil bo'ladi. Olingan ko'pgina ma'lumotlarning ko'rsatishicha, tipik bo'z tuproqlarda haydalma qatlam plastikligining quyi chegarasi 17-19% ni tashkil etadi, struktura hosil bo'lish namligi esa 19-20% o'rtasida o'zgarib turadi.

Xulosa:

Strukturani tiklashda termik omilning ham roli katta. Strukturaning vujudga kelishida harorat va suv asosiy omil hisoblanadi. Bu jarayon ta'sirini quyidagicha tushuntirish mumkin: Sovuq kunlar boshlanishidan oldin yoqqan yog'in suvlari yoki sug'orish suvlari tuproq kavaklariga kirib, ularni to'ldirishlari mumkin: haroratning keskin pasayib ketishi tufayli bu suvlar muzlaydi, muzlash suv xajmini kengaytiradi.

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volume-3| issue-1| 2025 published: |30-01-2025|

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166-171 pages

